

STRESS ANALYSIS AND COMPUTATION OF INTRINSIC FREQUENCY FOR REINFORCED COMPOSITE PLATE & SHELL STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

In order to analyse reinforced composite plate & shell structure author proposes a 3-node anisotropic isoparametric beam element forming a complete set with 8-node composite isoparametric shell element. This paper gives calculus formulas for geometric model, displacement, etc. of these elements. A corresponding computing software COMPSB is introduced, its main functions are described. The COMPSB has been used to analyse practical composite combined structures.

INTRODUCTION

A lot of reinforced composite plate & shell structures are needed to perform mechanical analysis in research works of some departments. The mechanical analysis of composite plate & shell structure has basically been completed in a previous work (Ref.[1]). In order to analyse reinforced composite plate & shell structures, it is necessary to introduce a bend beam element that forms a complete set with plate & shell element, and 3-node anisotropic isoparametric beam element is suitable for the structures. The calculation formulas of geometric model, displacement mode, strain, stress, stiffness matrix, etc. for this element have been derived. A corresponding computing software COMPSB (Composite Plate & Shell and Beam Computation) is developed and written in FORTRAN 77 language by our institute. The COMPSB has been used to compute an antenna array panel and a square cabin of composite materials. Main functions of the COMPSB are as follows:

1. Different geometric shapes of composite layered plate & shell structure can be suited.
2. Different faces of a structure are allowed to be subjected to different distributed load, and bearing loads contain body load, concentrated load, etc.
3. Different materials for different layers are allowed to use.
4. Different elastic parameters and physical parameters for reinforced beams are allowed to adopt.
5. The computed results, including displacement, stress and dynamic mode, can be displayed on the screen by colour map with the aid of graphic software.

FINITE ELEMENT STRESS ANALYSIS

In order to perform finite element analysis for different kinds of reinforced composite plate & shell structure, two elements have to be used. One is a composite isoparametric plate & shell element suited different geometric shape and changeability of shell thickness, the other is an anisotropic isoparametric bend beam element. They are introduced as follows:

8-NODE COMPOSITE ISOPARAMETRIC QUADRATIC SHELL ELEMENT

This element is Mindlin-type 8-node composite isoparametric quadratic shell element, it includes the coupling phenomenon between flexural bending & inplane stretching and the effect of shear deformation to suit different geometric shape and changeability of shell thickness. It is shown in Fig.1. The face of this element is a camber, the section along thickness direction is generated from straight lines. There are eight nodes at the mid-surface. We draw normal to mid-surface through each node i , the intersecting points with top surface and bottom surface are called a paired point of node i . By the use of shape functions $N_i(\xi, \eta)$ (Ref. [2]) and coordinates of the eight nodes of mid-surface a coordinate of any point in the element may be expressed by a natural coordinate as

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^8 N_i(\xi, \eta) \left(\begin{pmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{pmatrix} + \frac{t_i}{2} \zeta \bar{v}_{3i} \right) \quad (1)$$

here x_i, y_i, z_i are Cartesian coordinates of the eight nodes of a mid-surface of the element, t_i is the thickness of the element at node i , \bar{v}_{3i} is a unit normal vector that is perpendicular to the mid-surface at node i , it is decided from the coordinates of the paired point at node i . The selection rule of unit vectors $\bar{v}_{1i}, \bar{v}_{2i}$ is as following: $\bar{v}_{1i}, \bar{v}_{2i}$ and \bar{v}_{3i} compose a right-handed coordinate system. Several different selection method are given in Refs.[3-5].

Figure 1. Quadratic laminated shell element

In order to derive calculation formulas conveniently a creation of a local coordinate system $ox'y'z'$ at each point of the mid-surface of the element is rather useful. In the local coordinate system $ox'y'z'$ axis z' is a normal direction of the mid-surface. The key of the creation is a direction cosine vector \bar{v}_3 of the normal at each point of the mid-surface. One reasonable simple practice is that \bar{v}_3 is made by interpolation from the direction cosine vector \bar{v}_{3i} of the normal of the mid-surface at each node of the element, namely,

$$\bar{v}_3 = \sum_{i=1}^8 N_i \bar{v}_{3i} / \left| \sum_{i=1}^8 N_i \bar{v}_{3i} \right|$$

When \bar{v}_3 is defined, the direction cosine vectors \bar{v}_1, \bar{v}_2 of axes x', y' can be created in the same way. This element belongs to the degenerated three dimensional element subjected to two hypotheses about strain displacement relation. They are: 1) normal strain in thickness direction become zero; 2) the normal of mid-surface is still straight line under deformation, but no more retains normal. It means the normal of mid-surface \bar{v}_3 has rotations round \bar{v}_1 and \bar{v}_2 in deformation, let rotation angles are β and α respectively. And suppose all fibre layers have same rotation angle at the node. So that, a degree of freedom of node consists of the displacements u, v, w and the rotation angles α, β of the whole section. Let displacement vector of node i is

$$\{\delta_i\} = \{u_i, v_i, w_i, \alpha_i, \beta_i\}^T$$

the displacement of any point in the element can be obtained by interpolation with the aid of shape functions $N_i(\xi, \eta)$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^8 N_i(\xi, \eta) \left(\begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ w_i \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{t_i}{2} \zeta \bar{F}_i \right) \quad (2)$$

where

$$\bar{F}_i = [\bar{v}_{1i}, -\bar{v}_{2i}] \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_i \\ \beta_i \end{Bmatrix}$$

The calculation formulas about strain displacement relation, stress strain relation, elastic stress, elastic stiffness matrix, etc. are heavy and complicated, and they are omitted.

3-NODE ISOPARAMETRIC BEAM ELEMENT

This element is shown in Fig.2. XYZ is the global Cartesian coordinate system, rst is the natural coordinate system, namely $-1 \leq r, s, t \leq 1$ (Ref.[6]). The basic kinematic assumption is that plane sections originally normal to the center line axis remain plane and undistorted under deformation, but not necessarily normal to this axis.

In order to harmonize this element with the shell element a coordinates of mid-surface nodes of the element are determined from the coordinates of the paired points like above element, namely,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{Bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{Bmatrix}_{top} + \begin{Bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{Bmatrix}_{bottom} \right) \quad (3)$$

A local coordinate system $x'y'z'$ of the element must be created to define a coordinate and a displacement of any point in the element. Suppose unit vectors along axes x', y', z'

are $\bar{v}_r, \bar{v}_s, \bar{v}_t$ respectively. Reference point KK should be selected that it lies in a beam plane together with the element nodes. Creation process of the local coordinate system is omitted here. So that, the coordinates of any point in the element are:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^3 N_i(r) \left(\begin{Bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{b_i}{2} t \bar{v}_{ti} + \frac{a_i}{2} s \bar{v}_{si} \right) \quad (4)$$

where a_i, b_i are the thickness of the element in s, t direction respectively and

$$\begin{aligned} N_1(r) &= -r(1-r)/2 \\ N_2(r) &= 1-r^2 \\ N_3(r) &= r(1+r)/2 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2. Isoparametric beam element

Assume $\alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i$ are the rotation angles round $\bar{v}_{si}, \bar{v}_{ri}$ and \bar{v}_{ti} , we have the rotation vector

$$\bar{w} = \beta_i \bar{v}_{ri} + \alpha_i \bar{v}_{si} + \gamma_i \bar{v}_{ti}$$

Thus, the displacement of any point in the element are:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{Bmatrix} &= \sum_{i=1}^3 N_i(r) \left(\begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ w_i \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{b_i}{2} t [\bar{v}_{ri}, -\bar{v}_{si}] \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_i \\ \beta_i \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{a_i}{2} s [\bar{v}_{ti}, -\bar{v}_{ri}] \begin{Bmatrix} \beta_i \\ \gamma_i \end{Bmatrix} \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^3 N_i(r) \left(\begin{Bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ w_i \end{Bmatrix} + \left[\frac{b_i}{2} t \bar{v}_{ri}, \frac{a_i}{2} s \bar{v}_{ti} - \frac{b_i}{2} t \bar{v}_{si}, -\frac{a_i}{2} s \bar{v}_{ri} \right] \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_i \\ \beta_i \\ \gamma_i \end{Bmatrix} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Let displacement vector of node i is

$$\{\delta_i\} = \{u_i, v_i, w_i, \alpha_i, \beta_i, \gamma_i\}^T$$

Thus, we have brief displacement mode

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{Bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^3 [N_i]_{3 \times 6} \{\delta_i\} = [N]_{3 \times 18} \{\delta^e\}_{18 \times 1} \quad (6)$$

where

$$[N_i] = N_i(r) [I_{3 \times 3}, \frac{b_i}{2} t \bar{v}_{ri}, \frac{a_i}{2} s \bar{v}_{ti} - \frac{b_i}{2} t \bar{v}_{si}, -\frac{a_i}{2} s \bar{v}_{ri}]$$

The calculation formulas about strain, stress, stiffness matrix, etc. are heavy and complicated, and they are omitted.

There are different numbers of degree of freedom of node and different displacement modes for the shell element and the beam element. In order to certify coordination between two types of element necessary coordinate transformation relation needs to be derived. When the beam element occurs at intersection of two plates, the coordination is especially important. But the coordinate transformation relation contains many and diverse formulas, so they are cut out here.

COMPUTATION OF INTRINSIC FREQUENCY

It is well known that free vibration equation without damping is

$$[K]\{\delta\} + [M]\{\ddot{\delta}\} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Based on the equation (7) we have a equation solving intrinsic frequency of a structure

$$|[K] - \omega^2[M]| = 0 \quad (8)$$

where $[K]$ is a stiffness matrix of the structure, $[M]$ is a mass matrix of the structure. The mass matrix $[M]$ of the structure is obtained by assembling mass matrixes of all element. Calculation formula of the mass matrix of each element is

$$[m] = \iiint_{V_e} [N]^T \bar{\rho} [N] dV \quad (9)$$

where $\bar{\rho}$ is a mass density of material of that element, $[N]$ is shape function matrix of displacement of that element.

COMPUTATION EXAMPLES

Example 1. Stress analysis of three-layer composite simply supported square plate. For this plate span to thickness ratio is 20. The thickness of the middle layer is a half of the thickness of the outer layer. The fibre direction coincides with plate axis x in the outer

layers, and the fibre direction is in accordance with plate axis y in the middle layer. The plate is subjected to transverse sinusoidal load given by

$$q = \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{a}$$

where a is the length of sides of the square plate. Each layer is a unidirectional fibre reinforced composite having the following elastic constants:

$$\begin{aligned} E_T &= 6.894 \text{ GPa}, & E_L &= 25E_T, & G_{LT} &= 0.5E_T, \\ G_{TT} &= 0.4E_T, & \nu_{LT} &= \nu_{TT} = 0.25 \end{aligned}$$

When the computation is carried out, we take $a = 0.08m$, mesh division is 4×4 . Central deflection and maximum stresses are interesting results. These results are compared with exact elasticity solution and also with classical plate theory (Ref.[7]). The results are seen to be better than that obtained from classical thin plate theory.

Example 2. The computation of intrinsic frequency of transverse vibration of a rhombus plate. The computation model of the rhombus plate is shown in Fig.3. The model is composed of 96 nodes and 25 shell elements. The length of sides of the rhombus plate is $L = 0.1905m$, the thickness is $t = 0.0032m$. The material data are: $E = 71.705 \text{ GPa}$, $\mu = 0.33$, $\bar{\rho} = 2689.25 \text{ N} \cdot \text{s}^2/\text{m}^4$. The results are tabulated in Table 1. The results indicate that the intrinsic frequencies of the first four levels are approaching to analytic solution.

Figure .3. Computation model of transverse vibration of rhombus plate

Table 1. Intrinsic frequencies of transverse vibration of rhombus plate (Hz)

modal level	1	2	3	4
COMPSB	86.53	204.3	551.8	567.9
analytic solution	87.13	209.3	569.8	589.6
test value	83.50	195.0	521.0	556.0

Example 3. The computation of intrinsic frequency of lateral vibration of cantilever beam. The structure model is made of 10 beam elements. The height of section is $0.006m$, the width of section is $0.003m$, the length of the beam is $0.3m$. The material data are: $E = 71.098 \text{ GPa}$, $\mu = 0.33$, $G = 26.772 \text{ GPa}$, $\bar{\rho} = 2771.36 \text{ N} \cdot \text{s}^2/\text{m}^4$. The results are listed in Table 2. The results indicate that the computed values come near the analytic solution.

Table 2. Intrinsic frequencies of lateral vibration of cantilever beam(Hz)

modal level	1	2	3
COMPSB	52.78	340.90	953.60
analytic solution	54.61	347.52	957.24
SAP-5	54.47	339.70	945.70

Example 4. The computation of composite antenna array panel. The panel is a large rectangular composite plate. Its length is 4.7m, its height is 2.0m, its thickness is 0.105m. The panel is made of two outer layers and one middle thick layer. The outer layer is a layered plate which thickness is 0.0025m. The middle layer is polyurethane plate which thickness is 0.1m. The finite element mesh of the array panel is shown in Fig.4. The computing model is composed of 293 nodes, 84 shell elements and 66 beam elements. The nodes 147, 111 and 191 are three supported points.

Figure.4. Finite element mesh of the antenna array panel

The layered plate of the outer layer is made of surface felt, glass cloth, short cutting felt and glued resin. The reinforced beam is made of padauk. All material data are omitted here and can see in Ref.8. The load include gravity load and wind load. The gravity load is a sum of the dead weight of the panel and the weight of wave guide array system which is installed on the panel. The gravity load is 7845.32N. When wind direction is perpendicular with the panel the wind load reaches most serious situation. The strength of the wind load is calculated by the formula $p_n = 0.5 \cdot c \cdot \bar{\rho} \cdot v_n^2$, where c is a wind hindrance coefficient, $\bar{\rho}$ is mass density, v_n is the velocity of force n wind. The results include all node displacements, stresses at some points of every element, and intrinsic frequencies. The colour maps about displacement, deformation and stress are used to display these results. The intrinsic frequencies of the first three levels of the panel are 8.782, 10.82 and 22.86(Hz).

The results indicate that the distribution regular pattern of the displacement is correct. Biggest magnitude of displacement is obtained at the angle points on top of the panel. It reaches 0.009m as force 8 wind is blowing, and it reaches 0.023m as force 12 wind is blowing. The magnitudes of positive stresses at the outer layers and the sandwich are less than tensile strength σ_b , and the magnitudes of shear stresses are less than shear strength τ_b .

So a conclusion is drawn: the structure design of the antenna array panel is reasonable, the state of bearing forces is within the permitted limits. The computed results have been approved by the user.

The analysis and computation of the square cabin of composite materials are rather complicated, the computation report will be published separately.

CONCLUSION

The computations of several examined examples indicate that the results by the use of the computation technique proposed in this paper are in accordance with the exact solutions or the known results, and 3-node anisotropic isoparametric beam element is a better element that is satisfied for the reinforced composite plate & shell structures. This technique and software COMPSB possess strong applicability for composite complex combined structures.

In order to display the results we have designed and performed the software interfaces with graphical software INFEGAS and I-DEAS. Thus, the colour maps about displacement, stress and dynamic mode can be shown on the screen of a workstation or a PC computer. So that, the COMPSB is a software with the features of strong functions and good applicability, and is valuable to engineering application.

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